

Differentiate the personality profiles of the people of Sedati District, Sidoarjo regency who have been exposed to covid-19 from those who have not been exposed to Covid-19 during the Covid-19 pandemic era

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Abstract

This study was conducted with the aim of comparing the extrovert-introvert personality type of someone who has suffered from COVID-19 and who has never suffered from COVID-19 in the COVID-19 pandemic era in the Sedati District Sidoarjo community. The hypothesis of this study was that there was a personality type difference between people diagnosed with COVID-19 and without COVID-19. The research subjects were samples taken from the community of Sedati sub-district, Sidoarjo amounting to 150 people. The measuring instrument used was the extrovert- introvert personality scale Eysenck Personality Inventory (IPEI) (1977) which has been modified and translated. The purpose of this study was to compare the personality profile of the Sedati District Sidoarjo community who had been exposed to COVID-19 with people who were not affected by COVID-19 in the COVID-19 Pandemic Era. This study was a quantitative study with a cross-sectional design using self-administered and, interviewer-administered questionnaires with inclusion criteria of an age range of 20 years - 59 years, and fluent in reading and writing. The personality types of the people of Sedati District who have suffered from COVID-19 and the personality types of the people of Sedati District who have never been exposed to COVID-19 based on the results of the study show that there was no significant difference in personality type between those who have COVID-19 and those who don't have COVID-19.

Keywords: COVID-19; Psychological wellbeing; Personality type extrovert; Introvert

1. Introduction

Personality is a person's general attitudes, feelings, expressions, temperament, distinctive characteristics, and behavior. His attitude, feelings, expressions, and temperament will be seen in his actions when faced with certain situations. Personality is one of the biggest influences on success or failure in life, both in the field of work and in actions in society. Personality is very important for everyone to know so that the person can promote his strengths and improve the weaknesses that still exist.

Personality type is one of the factors that influence social interaction in society. Personality determines a person's specific adaptation to the environment (Allport 1971, in Sobur 2011). According to Jung (in Alwisol, 2009) there are two types of personality. First, those whose attention is more focused on themselves, or so-called introvert personalities. Second, those who seek the attention of others are called extroverted personalities. In everyday life there is interaction between a person and a group. Introverted personality types tend to be subjective experiences, focus on the inner and personal world where reality exists in the form of observation, withdrawn, and even unsociable. Introverted personalities are generally introverted and preoccupied with their inner life. Of course, they also observe

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the outside world, but they do it selectively, using a subjective view of them selves. Extrovert personality type brings a person to an objective experience, empathy in interacting positively and friendly with the people around him. Extroverted personalities care deeply about other people and the world around them, are active, relaxed and interested in the outside world.

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Personality can affect someone who has had COVID-19 or who has not had COVID-19 during an event, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. A person's personality can lead to the behavior carried out by that person, which can be infected with COVID-19. Based on the description above, research is needed to find out the personality profiles of the people of Sedati Subdistrict who have & have never been exposed to COVID-19 during the COVID-19 Pandemic Era (Sidoarjo Regency, 2021). Based on the background above, the formulation of the research problem is as follows "Are there differences in personality types who have suffered from COVID-19 and those who have never suffered from COVID-19 in the people of Sedati District in the Era of the Pandemic COVID-19.

2. Material and methods

This type of research was conducted in the form of quantitative research. With a cross section design (cross section). In this study, primary and secondary data will be collected from the dependent variable (COVID 19) and independent variables (Introvert and Extrovert Personality). The research schedule starts in May 2021 until October 2022, namely determining the title, until the research is complete. The research location is Sedati District, Sidoarjo Regency, and East Java.

This research design is used to examine an event at the same time (one time) so that the dependent variable and independent variable are studied simultaneously. The population in this study is the general public of Sedati District. In determining the size of the subject, the total population (N) can be seen from the list of the number of people in the Sedati District, totaling 109,831. How to determine the size of the subject is by using Consecutive Sampling. This study used a Questionnaire Sheet on the personality of the Extrovert and Introvert Personality Inventory (IPEI) with 30 validated question items. The values obtained in the personality type measurement scale indicate the subject's personality type. If the total score of extrovert personality answers is higher than the subject has an extrovert personality type. Vice versa, if the total score of introvert personality answers is higher than the subject has an introverted personality type.

3. Results and discussion

Sedati Sub-District is dominated by ponds/ referred to as a coastal area, but most of the factories are lined up along the Sedati Sub-District road. During the COVID-19 pandemic, most of the work in this sub-district continued to be carried out offline, but it did not rule out the possibility that some would also be online, there fore the COVID-19 rate in Sedati sub-district increased drastically in 2020.

3.1. Subject Demographic Characteristics

The results of the Reliability Test showed that the 15 indicators used on the extrovert personality variable 0.924 and the introvert 0.837 had a Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.6 . It can be concluded that all indicators measuring extrovert and introvert personality can be stated to have moderate levels and the results can be trusted. Validity test results The value of rtable is obtained from table r with $df = N-2$. Where N is the size of the subjects used in this study, namely as many as 30 people so that the rtable value = 0.349.

Table 1 Frequency Distribution of Subject Demographic Characteristics

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20-29 Years	70	58,3
30-39 Years	19	15,8
40-49 Years	20	16,7
50-59 Years	11	9,2
Total	120	100.0
Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Man	53	44,2
Woman	67	55,8
Total	120	100.0
EducationFinal	Frequency	Percentage (%)
SD/MIEqual	4	3,3
SMP / MTS Equivalent	5	4,2
SMA / MA Equivalent	102	85.0
S1	9	7,5
Total	120	100.0
Work	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Employee	19	15,8
Housewife	20	16,7
Student	42	35.0
Businessman	39	32.5
Total	120	100.0
Income n	Frequency	Percentage (%)
< Rp. 0	42	35.0
< Rp. 4,368,000	75	62.5
> Rp. 4,368,000	3	2,5
Total	120	100.0

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Not married yet	60	50.0
Marry	60	50.0
Total	120	100.0

Based on Table 1, the most age of the subjects is 20-39 years (58.3%), the most sex is female (55.8%). The most recent education was SMA/MA equivalent (85.0%). The most jobs are students (35.0%). Most income < Rp. 4, 368, 000,- (62.5%) and the most history of being exposed to COVID-19 is those who have never been exposed to COVID-19 (61.7%).

3.2. Identification of Personality Profiles of Sedati Sub-district Communities Who Have Suffered from COVID-19 in the Era of the COVID-19 Pandemic

Identification of the personality profile of the Sedati sub-district community who have suffered from COVID-19 in the COVID-19 pandemic era was measured using a questionnaire with a percentage of 100%.

Table 2 Frequency Distribution of Personality Test Scores in Subjects Who Have Suffered from COVID-19 based on Personality Type

No.	Personality type	Amount	Percentage (%)
1	extrovert	44	96%
2	introvert	2	4%
Amount		46	100%

Based on Table 2 above, it is known that most of the people in Sedati Subdistrict who had suffered from COVID-19 during the COVID-19 pandemic era mostly had extrovert personality types (96%) and the rest were introverted personality types.

Based on univariate analysis, most of the people in Sedati sub-district who suffer from COVID-19 have extroverted personality types, namely 44 subjects. Most of the subjects have introverted personality types, namely 2 subjects. The results of the analysis showed that most of the Sedati Sub district Subjects were extroverted personality types with the most extroverted personality types who had suffered from COVID-19. People with introverted personalities are more likely to follow COVID-19 health guidelines, potentially keeping them selves and their loved ones healthier. People with introverted personalities have a correlation with the desire to better follow COVID-19 prevention guidelines during the COVID-19 pandemic and also tend not to want to meet friends during the pandemic, while people with extroverted personalities still try to go out with other people (not following the recommended COVID-19 precautions) and are identified as frequently gathering for social activities. Extroverted personalities during the pandemic still prefer to spend time with their friends and loved ones (Lockett, 2022). The livelihood of the people of Sedati sub-district are fishermen, it is possible that they jointly sell fish to the market. The mothers are likely to jointly manage the clams caught by the fishermen in one house. This is what makes them suffer from COVID-19. They are also more likely to suffer from COVID-19 due to various activities outside the home such as recitations, RT RW meetings, neglecting to comply with the rules set by the government, due to negligence of disobedience to the rules. This makes it easier for them to suffer from COVID-19.

As Shokrkon and Nicoladis explained, subjects with extroverted personalities usually have stronger social relationships than introverted personalities, so they are more likely to interact with people during the COVID-19 pandemic crisis. People with extroverted personalities have wider social networks, which means that more support is available for them to communicate and relate to others. They also have higher relationship quality, experience more friendship satisfaction, and experience higher levels of social support (Shokrkon and Nicoladis, 2021).

3.3. Identification of Personality Profiles of Sedati Sub-district Communities Who Have Never Suffered from COVID-19 in the Era of the COVID-19 Pandemic

Identification of the personality profile of the Sedati sub-district community who have never suffered from COVID-19 in the COVID-19 pandemic era was measured using a questionnaire with a percentage of 100%.

Table 3 Frequency Distribution of Personality Test Scores in Subjects Who Have Never Suffered from COVID-19 Based on Personality Type

No.	Type Personality	Amount	Percentage (%)
1	extrovert	67	90%
2	introvert	7	10%
Amount		74	100%

Based on Table 3 above, it is known that most people in Sedati Subdistrict who have never suffered from COVID-19 during the COVID-19 pandemic era have an extrovert personality type of (90%).

The results showed that the subjects never suffered from COVID-19 in the COVID-19 pandemic era, namely having extrovert personality types, namely 67 subjects and introverted personality types, namely 7 subjects. These results indicate that more people with extrovert personalities have never suffered from COVID-19.

The number of research subjects who have extrovert personality is more than introvert personality. The results of this study also show that there is no significant relationship between personality type and a history of COVID-19, so that people with extroverted or introverted personalities may or may not suffer from COVID-19. For certain people, although there are extroverted personalities who tend to comply with health protocols and have sufficient knowledge about the transmission of COVID-19 that allows them to avoid infection with COVID-19 even though they have a high level of mobility and often go out with friends. This can be seen from the results of the study, it was found that the highest number of high school and university students had education. Knowledge about prevention efforts can be applied to your self so that you and your family are better protected. Increased knowledge will increase Subject awareness so that they will voluntarily comply with existing regulations or recommendations in preventing disease transmission, especially COVID-19 (Alimansur and Qyumi, 2020). Communities who have sufficient knowledge about COVID-19 can strengthen prevention and control measures together with the community, by increasing inter- and inter-related departmental communication and cooperation and conducting regular consultations, reporting epidemic developments in the community and discussing the application of prevention and control policies in society (Nurislaminingsih, 2020). 2020). Communities who have sufficient knowledge about COVID-19 can strengthen prevention and control measures together with the community, by increasing inter- and inter-related departmental communication and cooperation and conducting regular consultations, reporting epidemic developments in the community and discussing the application of prevention and control policies in society (Nurislaminingsih, 2020). 2020). Communities who have sufficient knowledge about COVID-19 can strengthen prevention and control measures together with the community, by increasing inter- and inter-related departmental communication and cooperation and conducting regular consultations, reporting epidemic developments in the community and discussing the application of prevention and control policies in society (Nurislaminingsih, 2020).

A person who has never suffered from COVID-19, whether he has an introverted or extroverted personality, usually tends to comply with the health protocol simple mented by the government to protect him self and those closest to him from contracting COVID-19 and maintai n a healthy body, immune system and mental condition so they are not vulnerable. Exposed to or infected with COVID-19. Government policy is a must that everyone obeys, so that everyone, both extroverted and introverted, must implement these provisions to prevent transmission of the virus so that the subject does not suffer from COVID-19 (Dewi, Setyani and Yulyanti, 2021). In terms of personality, people with introverted personality types have the potential not to suffer from COVID-19 because they have a basic attitude that doesn't like crowds (Ufi et al., 2021).

3.4. Comparing the Personality Profiles of Sedati Subdistrict People Who Have Suffered from COVID- 19 and Those Who Have Never Suffered from COVID-19 in the Era of the COVID-19 Pandemic

The Chi Square test is used to test whether there are differences in the personality types of subjects who have had COVID-19 and those who have never had COVID-19.

Table 4 Chi-Square Test Results for Differences in COVID-19 Status based on personality

COVID-19 history	Personality		p value
	introvert	extrovert	
Which	2	44	
Once			
Suffer			
COVID-19			
Who does not Once	7	67	0.487
Suffer			
COVID-19			

Based on Table 4 it can be concluded that "There is no significant difference between those who have suffered from COVID-19 and those who have never suffered from COVID-19 with extroverted and introverted personalities.

The results of this study indicate that there is no significant difference between COVID-19 history and personality type with a correlation value ($p=0.487$). It can be interpreted that subjects who have suffered from COVID-19 and who have never suffered from COVID-19 have no correlation with extroverted or introverted personalities. Efforts to isolate people with COVID-19 will not change the subject's personality. The main difference between extroverts and introverts is not in the behavioral aspect, but at the biological and genetic level. Personality type only allows the risk of transmission of COVID-19 to be greater, especially for people with extroverted personalities (Ariga, Amelia and Sari, 2018). The results of the study show that people with extroverted personalities are more likely to disobey the provisions for preventing COVID-19 because by nature they prefer to interact with crowds and their friends.

Each personality type, both introverted and extroverted, has certain difficulties in dealing with the COVID-19 pandemic, especially for those who have extroverted personalities who like to socialize and crowd but are restricted to prevent transmission of COVID-19. The results of the study concluded that introverts have higher levels of well-being during restrictions on public life, while people with extroverted personalities may lose some of their protective value for loneliness and well-being when opportunities to engage in social activities are limited (Gibler et al., 2021). It is based on the fact that extroverts are often judged to be easier to establish relationships with many people, considering that their open personality characteristics and speaking skills in general have great potential.

4. Conclusion

Based on the research above, the personality types of the people of Sedati District who have suffered from COVID-19 based on research show that most people have extrovert personality types 44 people (96%) 67 people (90%) have an extrovert personality type. There is no significant difference between those who have been exposed to and those who have never been exposed to COVID-19 and the extrovert and introvert personality types based on personality with a correlation value ($p=0.487$). It is recommended for subjects who have been exposed to COVID-19 in Sedati District to improve their preventive behavior against COVID-19 by complying with the health protocols that have been recommended by the government.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The First author states there is no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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